

Evidence Based Early Phase Design Recommendations Utilizing Knowledge Data Bases

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document- This format section allows the provision of the title of the Use-case along with a short text describing it and author details.

Title:

EU ASHVIN- Template

HELPING THE DESIGNERS IN THE EARLY DESIGN PHASES BY USING A KNOWLEDGE DATABASE WITH EVIDENCE-BASED DESIGN

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Evidence-based design for productivity, resource efficiency, and safety based on historical digital twin data

Project Status:

Finished

Publisher:

Please fill in

Author:

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Introduction:

This document provides background and describes a use case of the evidence-based design as a use case helping the footbridge designer in the early design phases to get a broad overview of the design space. With this overview, the designer is enabled to take an informed decision on which type of design should be investigated in more detail. The insights are provided to the user in three distinct categories as presented Predictions, Warnings, and Recommendations.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

Please fill in

Partners:

*Paul Merz (Technische Universität Berlin), Joan Evelyn Ongodia (Technische Universität Berlin),
Timo Hartmann (Technische Universität Berlin)*

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

Please fill in

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Helping The Designers In The Early Design Phases By Using Knowledge Database with Evidence-Based Design
Goal	Presenting an overview of the design options to support decision-making concerning the structure typology early in the design process by using digital twin data of former examples.
Description	Systematic evaluation of digital twin data regarding the effect on carbon footprint, construction costs, efficiency, construction time, and the safety of workers on site.
Input Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledgebase (digital twin data) of past projects that are large enough to be analyzed input parameters -construction length and width and typology - prefabrication space available -ability to deliver big parts
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a knowledgebase of past projects 2. Input 3. Analysing Output 4. Variation Input if possible 5. Analysing Output
Primary actors	Designers, Civil Engineers, Design Companies
Secondary actors	Architects
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of data of the site to generate designs
Trigger	Development of data based scenarios for optimal construction designs
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Every project
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to present the end-user with optimal construction designs for structures based on the historical digital twin data which is a digital model of a construction product from previous similar construction sites to increase productivity, resource efficiency, and safety.

Objectives:

This document provides for the Performance Indicators predictions for cost, construction time, and carbon footprint using linear regression models. The design personnel costs are Performance Indicators for the Key Performance Indicator cost, the personnel productivity during the construction phase is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator productivity and the Global Warming Potential (GWP) is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator resource efficiency.

Due to the very limited size of the dataset from previous examples, it is difficult to draw reliable conclusions from the prediction functions. Therefore, the very basic machine learning (ML) class of linear regression models was chosen to demonstrate the evidence-based design approach.

For each of the three Performance Indicators, five linear regression models with different predictors were created. The basic geometric dimensions of the structure length L , width W , and thickness T are used as predictors.

In the Machine Learning nomenclature, L , W , and T are the independent variables, while the Performance Indicator values for cost, productivity, and resource efficiency are the dependent variables.

The available data from a company can be analyzed and the potential for Machine Learning prediction models regarding cost, construction time, and carbon footprint can be discovered with these steps. Different linear regression models can be compared and the preferable geometric predictors for different Performance Indicator values can be identified.

The overall process shows the applicability of the approach even though the available database has major flaws which motivates the introduction of a digital twin as a standardized way of collecting data for future footbridge design and construction projects.

2.3 Overall Process:

The Evidence-Based Design use case interacts with the Performance Indicator assessment of solutions in the design space.

The overall process map for the use case is presented in Figure 2. Past construction data is collected in the knowledge database. The data files from the knowledge database should be processed first, after that the design task type should be chosen. Data cleansing and classification should be done. After this step, important data types should be defined. In the end, general mathematical equations can be created. After these steps, the results should be evaluated.

In the end, with the help of Evidence-Based use case, the results are evaluated easily. If they are not satisfied, same process can be done again. During all these activities, Evidence-Based Design use case provides; predictions, warnings, and recommendations.

Figure 2 Process Map

Implementation on #8 Footbridge in Germany

The City of Dortmund is planning to replace the existing Lindemannstrasse foot and cycle path bridge, which connects Max-Ophüls-Platz with the forecourt of the Dortmund Trade Fair Centre. The bridge crosses the Rheinlanddamm, a highly frequented inner-city main road with six lanes. 51°29'52.1"N 7°27'11.7"E are the coordinates of the footbridge location.

The database of historical footbridge projects used in this study was provided by project partner sbp. An overview of all nine files is given in Figure 3. The individual data files are analyzed and evaluated using diagrams. This section aims to showcase the entirety of all the data provided by sbp and identifies the data tables that are useful for further Evidence Based Design activities.

The database contains a total of 238 observations on footbridge projects with each 66 variables. A general problem of the database is the sparseness of the available data (see Figure 3) in addition to many variable values missing to make ample observations. Therefore, all predictions made on the basis of the available data are to be seen as examples of how to process the data when larger datasets are available.

File name	description
fb0_location	Location information including continent, country, city and geographic coordinates.
fb1_general_info	General information including architect, contractors, design scope and won awards.
fb2_basic_struct_prop	Basic structural properties including bridge type, material and ground conditions.
fb3_basic_geometry	Basic geometry including length, span, deck area and bridge type specific information.
fb4_timeline	Timeline information including project start/end, scope start/end and construction start/end.
fb5_design_team	Design team information including office location, partner and project manager
fb7_financial_aspects	Financial aspects including total cost, material cost and revenue design
fb9_text	Textual description of the bridge in German and English language
fb10_env_imp	Information on environmental aspects including global warming potential for excavation, structure, construction etc.

Figure 3 Overview of the sbp footbridge database

Figure 4 Overview of the sbp footbridge database

Figure 5 Number of bridges with the different bridge typologies (top left), Material used in the database (top right), Maximum span of footbridge projects grouped by bridge typology (bottom left), Correlation matrix of bridge typology and bridge material (bottom right)

The sbp footbridges can be distinguished in 10 different bridge typologies and they can be seen in Figure 5 top left. The maximum span of all bridges in the database is grouped by the bridge typology and can be seen in Figure 5 bottom left.

The bridge material is also present in the basic structural properties database. One bridge can have multiple materials. Figure 5 top right shows the number of bridges with different materials. It can be observed that cables, concrete, and steel are the most prominent materials within the sbp footbridge database. Over 70 bridges have components made of steel while about 50 bridges consist of concrete components. Less than half of the 83 total built bridges are constructed using cables.

Figure 5 bottom right shows the correlation between the bridge typology and the bridge material. Dark blue indicates no correlation while light blue is read as perfect correlation. As also discussed in the previous figure steel is the most prominent material being present in nearly every bridge typology with perfect correlation. Concrete is also distributed over nearly all bridge

typologies. The cables are only present in suspension, stress-ribbon, cantilever, cable net and cable stayed bridges.

Performance Indicator predictions for cost, construction time, and carbon footprint using linear regression models are summarized here. The design personnel costs are a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator cost, the personnel productivity during the construction phase is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator productivity and the Global Warming Potential (GWP) is a Performance Indicator for the Key Performance Indicator resource efficiency.

Due to the very limited size of the dataset, it is difficult to draw reliable conclusions from the prediction functions. Therefore, the very basic machine learning (ML) class of linear regression models was chosen to demonstrate the evidence-based design approach.

For each of the three Performance Indicators, five linear regression models with different predictors were created. The basic geometric dimensions bridge length L, bridge width W, and bridge thickness T are used as predictors.

In the ML nomenclature, L, W, and T are the independent variables, while the Performance Indicator values for cost, productivity, and resource efficiency are the dependent variables.

In Figure 5 predictors of the linear regression models for cost prediction can be seen.

Model	predictor(s)	Sample size
1	Bridge length L	54
2	Bridge width W	47
3	Bridge deck thickness T	28
4	Length, width, thickness without interaction	22
5	Length, width, thickness including interaction	22

Figure 5 Predictors of the linear regression models for cost prediction

The general formula for the cost prediction is presented below.

$$cost[€]=c_0+c_L \cdot L+c_W \cdot W+c_T \cdot T+c_{LW} \cdot L \cdot W+c_{LT} \cdot L \cdot T+c_{WT} \cdot W \cdot T+c_{LWT} \cdot L \cdot W \cdot T$$

In Figure 6 predictors of the linear regression models for construction time prediction can be seen.

Model	predictor(s)	Sample size
1	Bridge length	29
2	Bridge width	28
3	Bridge deck thickness	13
4	Length, width, thickness without interaction	12
5	Length, width, thickness including interaction	12

Figure 6 Predictors of the linear regression models for construction time prediction

The general formula for the construction time prediction is presented below.

$$time[days]=c_0+c_L \cdot L+c_W \cdot W+c_T \cdot T+c_{LW} \cdot L \cdot W+c_{LT} \cdot L \cdot T+c_{WT} \cdot W \cdot T+c_{LWT} \cdot L \cdot W \cdot T$$

In Figure 7 predictors of the linear regression models for carbon footprint prediction can be seen.

Model	predictor(s)	Sample size
1	Bridge length	19
2	Bridge width	17
3	Bridge deck thickness	7
4	Length, width, thickness without interaction	6
5	Length, width, thickness including interaction	6

Figure 7 Predictors of the carbon footprint models for construction time prediction

The general equation is shown below.

$$carbon\ footprint\ [kgCO_2e]=c_0+c_L \cdot L+c_W \cdot W+c_T \cdot T+c_{LW} \cdot L \cdot W+c_{LT} \cdot L \cdot T+c_{WT} \cdot W \cdot T+c_{LWT} \cdot L \cdot W \cdot T$$

The evidence-based design assistant is envisioned as a use case helping the footbridge designer in the early design phases to get a broad overview of the design space. With this overview, the designer is enabled to take an informed decision on which type of design should be investigated in more detail. There are three insights that are provided to the user. 1. Predictions 2. Warnings 3. Recommendations

Predictions are seen as numerical forecasts of Performance Indicator-Values based on the input of the user. The input of the user is derived from project requirements like the length of the footbridge and other boundary conditions like loading type and soil conditions. The predictions are made based on data from built footbridge projects.

By providing predictions of Performance Indicator values the use case enables the designer to take an informed decision on which kind of bridge typology might be further investigated. Predictions can be made in different Key Performance Indicator categories. The productivity Key Performance Indicator could be addressed using the construction time of past footbridge projects. Similarly, also the Cost Key Performance Indicator could be covered with the construction cost. For the Sustainability Key Performance Indicator, the Carbon Footprint of the Construction could be used.

Warnings are mostly connected to the Safety Key Performance Indicator to mitigate risks for construction workers. This is done by identifying critical combinations of input values that could lead to higher risks on the construction site. As some risks are very site specific another idea is to prompt the user with accidents that happened on the construction sites of similar projects to the one currently in design. This helps the design team to keep in mind potential risks and helps mitigate them.

Also, the other Key Performance Indicator warnings might be useful to show the risk of not staying within the desired ranges of cost, productivity, or resource efficiency.

For different bridge types, rough dimensions can be derived from the data of the existing structures. These are then referred to as recommendations. In addition to rough dimensions, a material recommendation can also be made. Furthermore, relevant standards for the dimensioning or regarding safety aspects on the construction site can be incorporated as a reference.

The user of the use case specifies the basic geometry of the new bridge to be designed in the use case. For the geometry, two initial values are used as a basis:

- Bridge length in [m]
- Bridge width in [m]

In most cases, these two values can be taken from the task description of a new footbridge to be designed. The ranges of the definition of the geometric input variables were derived from the minimum and maximum values of the bridges available in the Schlaich Bergermann Partner (sbp) database.

The last input present in the use case is the desired bridge typology. The user can thereby decide if the insights should be provided for a general footbridge or with regard to a specific bridge typology.

The inputs widget of the shiny application is shown in Figure 8.

Parameter Input

bridge length:
20 m 30 m 200 m
20 38 56 74 92 110 128 146 164 182 200

bridge width:
2 m 4 m 10 m
2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Prefabrication

prefabrication space available
 ability to deliver big parts

bridge typology
no selection ▼

Figure 8 Parameter input of the prototypical implementation of the Evidence Based Design Assistant

Under the evidence landscape, a small text tells the user how many footbridge projects were found for the specified typology. A screenshot of the evidence landscape in the shiny application is provided in Figure 9.

Predictions, Recommendations and Warnings based on the 5 most similar bridge projects from a total of 46 projects.

Figure 9 Evidence landscape in the prototypical Implementation of the Evidence Based Design Assistant

A screenshot of the prediction representation is shown in Figure 10. A red dot marks the prediction for the bridge currently under investigation based on the user input. The black dots show the five selected similar footbridge projects with larger dots implying greater similarity. Next to the graphical representation also numerical values are provided both as total values and normalized values per square meter deck area.

Construction Cost

Construction Time

Carbon Footprint

Figure 10 Predictions output in the prototypical implementation of the Evidence Based Design Assistant

Dimension recommendations are given for the different bridge typologies. These are currently based on quasi-linear relationships between input and output values. The only observable linear relationship is the pylon height based on the bridge span as shown in section 0. A screenshot of the respective widget is shown in Figure 11.

Dimension Recommendations

Figure 11 Screenshot of the dimension recommendations widget in the prototypical Implementation of the Evidence Based Design Assistant.

A screenshot of the warnings widget is shown in Figure 12. The prefabrication warning is currently active (red text) as a bridge type was chosen which would benefit from prefabrication.

Under the pictures of the 5 nearest bridges, the number of safety incidents is provided. If there were any safety incidents in the database these could be added here including a small description.

Warnings

A bridge of type girder would benefit from prefabrication, which is not possible on site. Maybe consider a different Bridge typology.

No accidents were recorded in the similar projects.

Selected similar projects

<p>1. nearest</p> <p>2945 Cost: 3,259 € Construction Time: 4 Days Embodied Carbon: 1,286 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>2. nearest</p> <p>3308 Cost: 3,927 € Construction Time: 2 Days Embodied Carbon: 886 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>3. nearest</p> <p>3560 Cost: NA € Construction Time: 3 Days Embodied Carbon: NA kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>4. nearest</p> <p>2215 Cost: 2,368 € Construction Time: NA Days Embodied Carbon: 190 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>5. nearest</p> <p>3222 Cost: 8,163 € Construction Time: 2 Days Embodied Carbon: NA kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>
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Figure 12 Warnings in the prototypical Implementation of the Evidence Based Design Assistant

Implementation on #11 Footbridge in Rathenow, Germany

Demonstration site #11 is a completed footbridge in the city of Rathenow, Germany. The footbridge consists of two arches and spans across the Havel River in a curved shape. The bridge has a total length of 350 m with the two main spans being 60 m and 48 m. Within the ranges of the arches, the bridge deck widens from the standard width of 3 m to an extended width of 4 m to allow for seating spaces.

The predictions tab for an arch bridge with length 350 m and a width of 3.5 m is found from the previous example interface. The predicted construction cost of ca. 9.2 million euros is much higher than the construction cost recorded for this bridge project in the database which is only about 5.5 million euros. This highlights again the current insufficient state of the database which is made transparent to the user in the evidence landscape in the bottom left corner of the use case. The predictions are only made based on a total of 6 projects which is not sufficient for reliable predictions.

The dimension recommendation is implemented for arch bridges recommending arch rises based in the span lengths. The longest span length of demo #11 is 60 m, which is input into the use case. The rise recommendation is calculated to 10 m which is shown on the right side of the screenshot. This corresponds well to the construction drawings of the footbridge as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Construction Drawing of demo #11 showing the main span length and arch rise

2.4 Disciplines:

*Design discipline- Architecture, Engineering, Design Support;
Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling*

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Outline conceptual design and full conceptual design.

Section 3: Process-definition

Life cycle stages: Outline conceptual design and full conceptual design

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

In Figure 14, exchange requirements among tools are shown. Past construction data is collected in the knowledge database. The data files from the knowledge database should be processed first, after that the design task type should be chosen. Data cleansing and classification should be done. After this step, important data types should be defined. In the end, general mathematical equations can be created. After these steps, the results should be evaluated. In the end, a parametric model can be generated and generative design process can be performed. As-Built design and digital twin data are sent to the knowledge database for performance indicator assessment.

Figure 14 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end